

**THE INEVITABLE PRESENCE OF ENGLISH WORDS IN THE LANGUAGE USED BY THE
TELECOMMUNICATION COMPANIES**

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to point out the relatively high presence of anglicisms in the advertising material used by the telecommunication and internet companies operating in Albania. A comparative study of the situation now to a few years ago shows that the use of English words is of the same frequency. Despite the development of these fields even in Albania, the institutions dealing with the official translation and standardization of words/terms are almost inexistent. Facing this reality, on the one hand, these borrowed words are the only means of transmitting the message in these fields serving as an enrichment to the language, on the other hand there has always existed the fear of language being threatened by the excess use of foreign words.

Keywords: anglicisms, telecommunication companies, internet companies, advertising material, English words, Albania

Introduction

Languages by responding to the changing need of communication as put by Fischer R Pulaczewska H (2008-1) and the need to express something, throughout centuries, have loaned and borrowed words. English having served for centuries as one of the interlingual medium of communication in Europe Fischer R Pulaczewska H (2008-1) and an international language and lingua franca worldwide, has had a considerably great influence in other languages.

Attitudes throughout the years towards English borrowed words have been both positive and negative. By many scholars, the influx of foreign words from any donor language is considered as threat to the recipient language. Fischer R Pulaczewska H (2008-11), went beyond, by writing about warnings for future language death due to English influence sometimes caused by strong national feelings. This fear is also expressed by Albanian linguists too such as Shkurtaj Gjovalin (2017-15) stating that one big threat to language is caused by an overestimation of the foreign element and an underestimation of the national culture in general (highlighting mostly the cases of duplication, which can easily be resolved by opting for the exact Albanian equivalent instead of using the foreign word). The latest development related to the purification of languages is that of the Italian government which proposed sanctions for anyone using English or other foreign words in official communication as a measure to protect Italian from what is considered 'Anglomania'. Shkurtaj (2017-15) points out that the Albanian language is directly threatened and put into danger by the State's disregard and lack of care and by the non-edited and uncorrected publications. In Albania there is no official authority in charge of the linguistic entries/their equivalents in a

language, leading to an uncontrolled entrance of foreign words (new or duplicates) and their standardization. In France, Jean-Marie Rouard, writer and member of the French Academy when talking about the English words entering French states that *"The whole of these words pollutes the French language very seriously. Over time, they will lead to its destruction"*. In German speaking countries language associations provide a list of reasons why anglicisms should not be welcomed in German Julia Weithaler (2014:15) as the following: English words impede communication, threaten German identity and culture, destroy language diversity by surprising the more adequate German expressions, they lead to the formation of privileged class who are the ones that understand English etc.

On the other hand, the continuous use and spread of English words indicates that there are many articles/services introduced on a daily basis which are named in English and considered by Haspelmath M (2009-46) as 'cultural borrowings', because it is believed to be the easiest means of communication and understanding among peoples. Anglicisms as supported by Shkurtaj Gj (2017-63) have become inevitable in Albanian by standing out from the other loan words used in Albanian due to the English language effect on Albanian as the first foreign language learned/taught nationwide and the extra-linguistic factors. Shehu I (2016-27) attitude towards anglicisms in a study done on the foreign terms used in the field of telecommunication is that of an enrichment to the language/terminology when there is no equal Albanian equivalent especially in advance science and technology, which is the major reason nowadays associated to linguistic borrowings.

The Corpus is taken from advertising materials, brochures, leaflets, fliers and websites of official telecommunication or internet companies.

The presence of English words in the telecommunication and IT language.

In the first years of the introduction and use of mobile devices in Albania and with the use of the computer and the Internet, any instructions and programs were mainly in English. Today most people, mostly the new generation, are already used to the programs on their phones or i-pods in English. English itself is an 'obligation' for anyone who continues one's postgraduate degree studies or claims to attend universities abroad and the use of different programs either the computer or the smart phones, is very necessary and at the same time very simple for them. It is the older generation the one to face a great challenge when it comes to using technological devices, not only with English which has become indispensable especially after '90, but with the devices as well, since they were freshly introduced to them. However, nowadays even the older generation has fallen into the trap of technology, with the widespread and excessive use of social media. Given the difficulties faced by this non-English speaking generation, both telephone and computer companies have tried to launch computer and telephone programs in the market in recent years, in the Albanian language. Today in Albania you can have a mobile phone with programs in Albanian language, the menu of which is in Albanian.

One such phone is offered by the mobile phone company Vodafone, Vodafone Smart First 6 Shehu I (2016-30). The phone menu is in the Albanian language (although it should be emphasized not all of it) which means that on the screen we see terms like 'cilësimet' for (settings), 'fotoaparati' for (camera), 'e-postë' for (e-mail), 'galeria' for (gallery), 'kontakte' for (contacts), 'kalendar' for (calendar), 'tingulli' for (sounds), 'rrjetet pa tel' for (wireless networks), 'shfletues' for (browser) etc.

There you also find Albanian and English combinations of certain collocations such as: 'version i firmware-it' for (firmware version), 'version Kernel' for (Kernel version) etc. And sometimes, some of the terms are in English such as the case of : update, protect, my Vodafone, google settings etc.

The number of words that enter the telecommunication terminology is relatively high since it is a field the language of which is used by everyone, even non-specialists. Terminology, whether Albanian or borrowed, of this field is inevitable and used daily since telecommunication tools are mostly used in our daily lives where we would single out the phone (non-landline), for which we all use the term 'celular'. (From English cellphone). This term in Albanian is widely used, not by everyone only by specialists but also by non-specialists and its definition in the Albanian language dictionary of 2006 is: 'small hand-held telephone').

Reasons for borrowings.

A good part of these terms have entered the Albanian language with the introduction of some companies in Albania, international telephone companies such as Vodafone and One, as well as with the opening of the

telecommunication and IT departments at Universities where students could attend their studies in the respective branches. etc. In the written language used by these companies, we often encounter expressions of the type: mobile phone, dërgo një sms, bluetooth, video conference, chat, shërbimi Camel (Customized Applications for Mobile Networks Enhanced Logic), roaming etc. These terms are often used in the Albanian language, with the introduction of new services from these companies, new concepts which as a result are expressed in foreign terms, specifically in English terms, either because of these concepts, items or services there is no equivalent in the Albanian language, or as a result of the influence of the language from where the item or service originated or was invented, specifically from English-speaking countries. It happens that these terms are present since it is simpler to use ready foreign terms instead of Albanian ones.

It is thought that one of the reasons for use of foreign terms instead of Albanian ones in the field of telecommunications is that these companies that provide telephone services, operate not only in Albania. They are international, and being such, they want the language and terms used to be the same in all the countries where they operate, so as not to risk using the wrong concept of a term if the latter is 'Albanianised'. Normally, the language or terms as study elements are not the responsibility of companies, but if work is being done to translate them or give an Albanian equivalent (if there is one) from researchers and linguists without any conceptual change, and if their publications are edited and anglicisms are replaced, where possible, with the term in Albanian, then these foreign words would be under control. In the below listed examples taken from the language used by Vodafone Albania company you will notice the high presence of English words such as: *Vodafone "e-top up"; "roaming" me parapagese; shërbimi 'camel'; Vodafone 'mobile broadband'; 'online' kudo ndodheni; internet me shpejtësi shumë të lartë në 'laptopin' tuaj; Si mund ta 'aksesoni My Vodafone?; me aplikacionin më të ri My Vodafone ju mund të kontrolloni falas në çdo moment balancën tuaj; paketat që ju perdorni; "SMS or MB" si dhe të informoheni për gjithçka rreth komunikimit tuaj; çfarë mund të bëj në lidhje me kërcënimin nëpërmjet mjeteve elektronike të komunikimit ('cyberbullying')* etc.

Comparative study of the foreign words used within a 10 year period.

When taking into account quantity, the number of English words used and their frequency within the years is relatively the same, despite minor changes such as the case of the previously used phrase 'on line top-up' which is nowadays partially translated and used as 'rimbushje'-(replacing top-up) on line'. When looking at the language used either in the printed leaflets or the online website of the companies, the reader encounters words/phrases such as :*Logohuni* (for 'log in'-adapted to the Albanian morphological system), *e-commerce*, *SOS credit top-up*, *shërbimi Data SOS*, *Vodafone Basic*, *Vodafone Easy*, *Vodafone Advanced*, *Tourist Pack*, *Shtëpia Unlimited*, *kontent (for content)*, *VOD Video on Demand*, *Catch -up Tv*, *distributor (for distributor)*, *inovative (innovative)*, *miksohen (mixed)*,

router, karte smart, bli online, prize smart, kamera wireless, navigim, video streaming etc.

Conclusions

Despite the development of this field, yet there is a lack of a bilingual dictionary drafted by the professionals of the field and the linguists, which would somehow help with the standardization process of the language used in the textbooks and any other materials used by the telecommunication companies. Even though sometimes not understandable for certain generations and to a certain degree damaging to our language, yet from our point of view, these foreign words constitute a large part of the terminology of the field and they are essential to the understanding of the professionals among themselves first and to the ordinary people to whom life is unimaginable without technological devices.

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